

Self-assembly of hydrogen-bonding networks of *N*-9-alkyladenine

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A series of *N*-9-alkyladenines, which can self-assemble through hydrogen bonding networks, have been synthesized. *N*-9-Dodecyladenine and *N*-9-tetradecyladenine have been characterized by X-ray crystallography and direct observation using scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM).

Hydrogen bond plays an important role in the chemistry of life, being involved, for instance, in various types of molecular self-assembly and molecular recognition, and has attracted much attention as a key methodology to form spontaneously stable and structural well-defined nanostructure¹. Scanning tunnelling microscopy (STM) investigation of DNA base molecules deposited on the clean substrate is a very important subject because DNA is constructed by hydrogen-bonded complementary base pairs, which hold together the two helical chains of nucleotides in DNA and form the basis of the genetic code. The molecular self-assembly mechanism was investigated by STM in ambient conditions because that was usually investigated in an ultra-high vacuum (UHV) and at low temperature². In order to study alkane-assisted adsorption and self-assembly of DNA base molecules, we have prepared purine derivatives with long-chain alkyl groups. Here, we report the syntheses of a series of *N*-9-alkyladenines. *N*-9-Dodecyladenine and *N*-9-tetradecyladenine have been characterized by X-ray crystallography and direct observation using STM. We observed their two-dimensional self-assembly formations on the surface of graphite by STM in ambient conditions with high resolution.

Results and Discussion

A series of *N*-9-alkyladenines were prepared in good yields in two steps (Scheme 1). Both *N*-9-dodecyladenine and *N*-9-tetradecyladenine were crystallized as thin platelets from CHCl₃/MeOH solution. The crystals were stable

Scheme 1

in ambient conditions. Successful X-ray diffraction analyses of their single crystals (Table 1) show that both crystallize in monoclinic space group $P2_1/c$. There are four molecules in the unit cell. Their atom numbering and the crystal structure are given in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. Their crystal packing patterns show a zigzag structure in which the alkyl chains are arranged in an antiparallel way (Figs. 3 and

Table 1. Experimental data for the diffraction studies of *N*-9-dodecyladenine and *N*-9-tetradecyladenine

	<i>N</i> -9-Dodecyladenine	<i>N</i> -9-Tetradecyladenine
Empirical formula	C ₁₇ H ₂₉ N ₅	C ₁₉ H ₃₃ N ₅
Mr	303.45	331.50
<i>T</i> (K)	293(2)	293(2)
Space group	$P2_1/c$, monoclinic	$P2_1/c$, monoclinic
<i>a</i> (Å)	19.507(4)	21.0715(5)
<i>b</i> (Å)	8.192(2)	8.1658(2)
<i>c</i> (Å)	11.474(2)	11.5584(2)
β (°)	104.32(3)	98.9323(13)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1776.6(6)	1964.68(8)
<i>Z</i>	4	4
<i>D_c</i> (g cm ⁻³)	1.135	1.121
Crystal size (mm)	0.15 × 0.35 × 0.04	0.28 × 0.40 × 0.40
μ (Mo-K α)/mm ⁻¹	0.070	0.069
<i>F</i> (000)	664	728
θ (°) range	2.15–25.00	3.49–27.87
<i>h, k, l</i> ranges	–23 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 22, –9 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 0, 0 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 13	–27 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 27, –10 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 10, –15 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 15
Data/restraints/parameters	3113/0/201	4663/0/218
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0447, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.127	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0538, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1487
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0968, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1563	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0860, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1682
Goodness of fit on <i>F</i> ²	0.913	1.028
Final $\Delta\rho$ (e/Å ³) max, min	0.001, 0.000	0.000, 0.000

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of *N*-9-dodecyladenine showing components of molecules

Fig. 2. Crystal structure of *N*-9-tetradecyladenine showing components of molecules

4). It should be noted here that these arrangements are stabilized by intra-layer hydrogen-bonding networks. Bond length and angle data for both of them agree with previously reported crystal structure of 9-methyladenine³. The distances between two adjacent alkyl chains are 4.10 Å for *N*-9-dodecyladenine and 4.12 Å for *N*-9-tetradecyladenine. The alkyl chain and the purine ring in both of them are not coplanar in the crystal structure, and the alkyl chains make an angle of 35° with the purine rings.

In accordance with the crystal structures, we find two principal modes of interaction in their crystals (Figs. 3 and

4): for *N*-9-dodecyladenine, interpurine hydrogen bonds of the type N(10)-H(101)...N(1) [N(10)-H(101) = 0.9352(17), H(101)-N(1) = 2.0849(17), N(10)...N(1) = 2.9750(20) Å, N(10)-H(101)...N(1) = 158.56(11)°] and N(10)-H(102)...N(7) [N(10)-H(102) = 0.9868(16), H(102)-N(7) = 2.1334(17), N(10)...N(7) = 3.1080(20) Å, N(10)-H(102)...N(7) = 168.99(12)°], while for *N*-9-tetradecyladenine, interpurine hydrogen bonds of the type N(10)-H(101)...N(1) [N(10)-H(101) = 0.9000(15), H(101)-N(1) = 2.1381(13), N(10)...N(1) = 2.9662(17) Å, N(10)-H(101)...N(1) = 152.62(10)°] and N(10)-H(102)...N(7)

Fig. 3. Molecular packing of *N*-9-dodecyladenine, representing the intra-layer hydrogen-bonding networks

Fig. 4. Molecular packing of *N*-9-tetradecyladenine, representing the intra-layer hydrogen-bonding networks

[N(10)-H(102) = 0.9000 (12), H(102)-N(7) = 2.2444 (15), N(10)...N(7) = 3.1149(16) Å, N(10)-H(102)...N(7) = 162.60 (11)°]. It is noteworthy that the interaction is asymmetric^{4,5}.

We also confirmed the structural assignment by performing a direct observation of using STM (Figs. 5 and 6). Their STM images adsorbed on a freshly cleaved surface of highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) show a monolayer with periodicities of 3/10 nm × 0.44 nm for *N*-9-dodecyladenine, and a monolayer with periodicities of 3.20 nm × 0.45 nm for *N*-9-tetradecyladenine. The bright areas (high tunnelling current) correspond to the purine ring, while the dark areas (low tunnelling current) to the long-chain alkyl group⁶. For *N*-9-dodecyladenine, the length of long-chain alkyl

Fig. 5. STM image of a monolayer of *N*-9-dodecyladenine deposited on graphite image size 12 50 × 12 50 nm, $V_s = -843$ mV, $I = 1.29$ nA. It may be noted that the STM image has been filtered with a low-pass filter to remove high-frequency noise

Fig. 6. STM image of a monolayer of *N*-9-tetradecyladenine deposited on graphite, image size 12 27 × 12 27 nm, $V_s = 686$ mV, $I = 1.14$ nA. It may be noted that the STM image has been filtered with a low-pass filter to remove high-frequency noise

groups is 16.5 Å, and the distance of nearest-neighbor alkyl groups arranged in an antiparallel way is 4.40 Å, which correlates with that (4.10 Å) in the crystal structure. Whereas for *N*-9-tetradecyladenine, the length of long-chain alkyl groups is 18.2 Å. The long-chain alkyl groups appear to be visible and the distance on nearest-neighbor alkyl groups is 4.50 Å, which correlates with that (4.12 Å) in the crystal structure. The purine ring could not be resolved, indicating some dynamic conformational disorder.

The crystal structures presented here show that *N*-9-alkyladenine can self-assemble through hydrogen bonding networks, which are the same as adenine and the STM results also show that dodecyl and tetradecyl chains are sufficiently long to form and stabilize self-assembled monolay-

ers at the substrate surface by increasing the adsorbate-substrate interaction.

Experimental

N-9-Dodecyladenine : A suspension of adenine (1 g, 7.5 mmol) and 50% oily sodium hydride (0.38 g, 7.8 mmol) in DMF (100 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 1.5 h. To the solution was added $C_{12}H_{25}Br$ (2.0 g, 8.0 mmol). After stirring for 24 h at 100° , the solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue purified by column chromatography on silica gel using $CH_3OH-CHCl_3$ (1 : 9) as eluent. 9-Dodecyladenine was obtained in 78% yield (Found : C, 67.53; H, 9.45; N, 23.55. $C_{17}H_{29}N_5$ calcd. for : C, 67.29; H, 9.63; N, 23.08%); 1H NMR (200 MHz; $CDCl_3$) δ 8.34 (1H, s, H-2), 7.92 (1H, s, H-8), 7.27 (2H, br s, NH_2), 4.22 (2H, t, CH_2N), 1.24–1.89 (20H, m, CH_2), 0.87 (3H, m, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 154.7, 151.0, 149.8, 140.9, 119.4, 96.1, 44.1, 31.9, 30.1, 29.6, 29.4, 29.3, 29.0, 26.6, 22.7 and 14.1; AEI-MS m/z (%) 303 (70) [M^+], 274 (10), 260 (18), 246 (20), 232 (10), 218 (22), 204 (42), 190 (69), 176 (30), 162 (32), 149 (100), 135 (70). Single crystal suitable for X-ray diffraction was obtained readily by slow evaporation of a $CHCl_3/MeOH$ solution.

N-9-Tetradecyladenine : It was synthesized by using the above procedure using adenine (1 g, 7.5 mmol), 50% oily sodium hydride (0.38 g, 7.8 mmol) and $C_{14}H_{29}Br$ (2.2 g, 8.0 mmol), in 74% yield (Found : C, 68.78; H, 10.00; N, 21.19. $C_{19}H_{33}N_5$ calcd. for : C, 68.84; H, 10.03; N, 21.13%); 1H NMR (200 MHz; $CDCl_3$) δ 8.37 (1H, s, H-2), 7.86 (1H, s, H-8), 6.58 (2H, br s, NH_2), 4.21 (2H, t, CH_2N), 1.15–1.89 (24H, m, CH_2), 0.88 (3H, m, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 154.7, 151.2, 149.8, 140.9, 119.4, 96.1, 44.1, 31.9, 30.1, 29.6, 29.4, 29.3, 29.0, 26.6, 22.7 and 14.1; AEI-MS m/z (%) 331 (65) [M^+], 316 (4), 302 (10), 288 (10), 274 (13), 260 (17), 246 (20), 232 (18), 218 (27), 204 (53), 190 (76), 176 (35), 162 (36), 149 (100), 135 (65). Single crystal suitable for X-ray diffraction was obtained readily by slow evaporation of a $CHCl_3/MeOH$ solution.

N-9-Hexadecyladenine : It was synthesized by using the above procedure using adenine (1 g, 7.5 mmol), 50% oily sodium hydride (0.38 g, 7.8 mmol) and $C_{16}H_{33}Br$ (2.4 g, 8.0 mmol) in 76% yield (Found : C, 70.20; H, 10.20; N, 19.85. $C_{12}H_{37}N_5$ calcd. for : C, 70.15; H, 10.37; N, 19.48%); 1H NMR (200 MHz; $CDCl_3$) δ 8.36 (1H, s, H-

2), 7.86 (1H, s, H-8), 6.44 (2H, br s, NH_2), 4.21 (2H, t, CH_2N), 1.25–1.89 (28H, m, CH_2), 0.88 (3H, m, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 155.5, 152.8, 149.9, 143.9, 140.2, 119.4, 63.7, 62.6, 51.3, 43.9, 32.8, 31.8, 29.6, 29.3, 29.0, 26.6, 26.4, 26.2, 25.8, 22.6 and 14.0; AEI-MS m/z (%) 359 (45) [M^+], 330 (3), 316 (4), 302 (4), 288 (4), 274 (5), 260 (6), 246 (8), 232 (8), 218 (10), 204 (20), 190 (31), 176 (14), 162 (15), 149 (52), 135 (37).

N-9-Octadecyladenine : It was synthesized by using the above procedure using adenine (1 g, 7.5 mmol), 50% oily sodium hydride (0.38 g, 7.8 mmol) and $C_{18}H_{37}Br$ (2.6 g, 8.0 mmol) in 73% yield (Found : C, 71.39; H, 10.73; N, 18.20. $C_{23}H_{41}N_5$ calcd. for : C, 71.27; H, 10.66; N, 18.07%); 1H NMR (200 MHz; $CDCl_3$) δ 8.35 (1H, s, H-2), 8.11 (1H, s, H-8), 6.72 (2H, br s, NH_2), 4.23 (2H, t, CH_2N), 1.18–1.89 (32H, m, CH_2), 0.88 (3H, m, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz; $CDCl_3$) δ 155.1, 152.1, 150.0, 140.7, 119.6, 96.1, 44.0, 31.9, 30.1, 29.7, 29.4, 29.0, 26.6, 26.4, 22.7 and 14.1; AEI-MS m/z (%) 387 (72) [M^+], 358 (8), 344 (9), 330 (9), 316 (11), 302 (12), 288 (11), 274 (14), 260 (20), 246 (21), 232 (19), 218 (28), 204 (52), 190 (71), 176 (33), 162 (37), 149 (100), 135 (56).

The STM experiments were performed on Nanoscope IIIa SPM (Digital Instruments, U.S.A.) in ambient conditions. STM tips were mechanically formed PtIr wire (90/10). The sample was dissolved in toluene (HPLC grade, Aldrich) with a concentration of less than one percent. A droplet of the solution was deposited onto a freshly cleaved surface of HOPG.

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